

Formulation of Novel Herbal Based Tea Mixture for Cold, Cough

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ABSTRACT

My research aims to formulate a novel herbal based tea mixture using different natural extracts, including Darjeeling tea leaf extract, Psidiumguajava fruit extract, licorice extract, ginger root extract, apple fruit extract, and rose flower extract. The formulation involved combining these extracts in standard quantities to create a proper blend that offers potential health benefits like relief from cold,cough. The materials and methods of the extraction and preparation techniques used for each of my ingredient. The results and discussion presents the clear and proper findings of the study, including the phytochemical composition and potential therapeutic properties of the formulated tea leaf mixture. My individual research contributes to the development of natural and herbal based tea products with potent applications in the field of Pharmacy.

INTRODUCTION

In present years, there has been an increasing research interest in natural and herbal remedies due to their potent health and Medicinal benefits and minimal side effects. Traditional herbal medicines have been used for centuries and continue to serve as a source of inspiration for the development of new therapeutic uses. As One proper area of research interest is the formulation of herbal based tea leaf mixtures that combine the benefits of various plant extracts. This study focuses on the formulation of a novel herbal-based tea mixture using Darjeeling tea leaf extract, Psidiumguajava fruit extract, licorice extract, ginger root extract, apple fruit extract, and rose extract. Each of these ingredients are known for its unique phytochemical composition and potent therapeutic properties. By combining them in specific proportions, we aim to create a proper blend that maximizes their individual benefits and offers a broader range of health promoting effects.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

I collected this materials from Malbazar after i did this research perfectly.Darjeeling Tea Leaf Extract (30gm)- The tea leaves obtained from a reputable source and subjected to proper water extraction. The extracts then concentrated and standardized to obtain the proper desired concentration. PsidiumGuajava Fruit Extract (10gm)- Ripe guava fruits were collected by lab from Malbazar and processed to extract the bioactive components.The extraction of this method involved maceration in a suitable solvent followed by filtration and concentration.

Licorice Extract (7.5gm)-Licorice roots were properly procured and properly processed by using an appropriate solvent extraction method.The resulting extract was then purely concentrated and properly standardized to achieve the desired concentration. Ginger Root Extract (5.5gm)- Fresh ginger roots first washed, peeled, and finely chopped.The extraction was carried out by using a pure suitable solvent, and the extract was concentrated and standardized. Apple Fruit Extract: (2.5gm): Ripe apples were collected by Malbazar after this will be washed, diced, and subjected to extraction using a suitable solvent.The resulting of this For this research extracts was concentrated and standardized.

Rose Extract (4.5gm): Rose petals were collected by Malbazar and subjected to extraction using an appropriate solvent.The extract was then properly concentrated and standardized. The individual extracts obtained from the above materials were combination in specific proportions to create the herbal based tea mixture. The proportions determined based on a good and unique research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formulation herbal based tea leaf mixture exhibited a proper complex phytochemical profile, combining the bioactive compounds present in Darjeeling tea leaves, guava fruits, licorice roots, ginger roots, apples, and roses. The proper

Analysis of the mixture revealed the presence of polyphenols, flavonoids, antioxidants, and other potentially beneficial compounds. These phytochemicals totally contribute to the antioxidant, antiinflammatory, antimicrobial, and other therapeutic properties of the mixture.

PH-The formulation pH will be 5.7(SHIBANJAN PAUL ROY ET AL)

Invivo Study-I grouped it by taking the consent letter of three persons Group1 Control Group2 Standard i used the marketed tea Group3 my formulation name Kanu"stea the three persons had slightly cough and cold.Control group i didn't give any formulated tea soo after 30min not stop sneezing, coughing after standard group very less sneezing and coughing very slightly after by Kanu"steasneezing,coughing totally stop.but according my knowledge further clinical trial required. The formulation of Darjeeling tea leaf extract and Psidiumguajava fruit extract provides a rich source of antioxidants, which may aid in combating oxidative stress and reducing the risk of heart related diseases. Licorice extract contributes to the mixture's potent antiinflammatory and immunomodulatory effects. Ginger root extract gives us digestive and antinausea properties. Apple fruit extract adds a touch of antimicrobial activities and rose extract gives a wounderfulflavour.

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